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More power to physiotherapy

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Abstract

For a hundred years, medicine has been based on biochemistry. That has now reached its limits. Drugs, all drugs, have side effects. Healing problems that these drugs cannot cure is now possible with biophysics using pressure and electricity without poisons or opening the body. The results are safe and spectacular.

This article examines the benefits of biophysics for physiotherapists who are now able to achieve more by using better tools.

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The right tool for the job

The traditional view of physiotherapy is that it teaches a few simple exercises and by pressing with fingers some pain can be alleviated. Worse than that, a physiotherapist is said to be inferior to an orthopaedic surgeon.

Whether that was ever true, it certainly is not now. Instead of pressing with fingers, the physiotherapist has a new tool in CellSonic that performs non-invasive surgery, does not use drugs and has no side effects. Patients come in bent and walk out straight.

Quite apart from the benefits to patients, the status of physiotherapy is enhanced, the business improved and earnings increased. With their knowledge of the anatomy, all a physiotherapist needs to master the new technology is a few minutes training on how to

operate the machine and then they are working inside the body from the outside.

Cellsonic VIPP (very intense pressure pulses) damage or provoke. This is a simplification because the complete explanation is complicated. Damage is done to infection, germs are killed, calcifications shattered and blockages released. Provocation is the stimulation of the immune system to make a repair by bringing stem cells to the site, increasing vascularisation and blood cells. Muscles are enhanced and nerves repaired. Additionally, and very simply, the replication of mutant cells is stopped and they then only replicate healthy cells. In other words, cancer is stopped without drugs, non-invasively and without side effects.

It takes a physiotherapist five minutes to realise that they can do more than they were trained to

do. Quite apart from curing cancer, which is the easiest treatment to perform, an athlete can be given a 13% improvement in performance. A geriatric marooned in bed with a catheter and pressure sore can be restored to mobility and dignity. Half the population all of whom have lower back pain can be relieved. What cannot be done easily is to placate orthopods who sense that physios have encroached on their patch. CellSonic has no apologies.

Safety

The story of CellSonic is one of discovery. It started with breaking kidney stones with sound waves forty years ago. This is now done in all hospitals of the world and millions of patients have been treated safely. Since then the technology has changed, the machines became smaller, weaker, hand held and cost much less. New applications were reported by customers, usually doing something that was not recommended but they thought they would try it. The fact that CellSonic has no side effects made everything possible. This is unique in medicine where all drugs have side effects [1-7].

Conclusion

Gone is the notion that the body is the sum total of its chemistry. The pharmaceutical industry still has an important role to play but it is no longer the only force in medicine. Biochemistry is giving way to biophysics.

References

1. Hague A. 2017. Review of reports of curing cancer with Cell Sonic VIPP machines. Gen Med Open 1. Ref.: <https://bit.ly/34Ec92S>
2. Andrew Hague. 2019. Pain: Physical and Emotional. J Complement Med Alt Healthcare. Ref.: <https://bit.ly/2Z1s6iq>
3. Andrew Hague. 2019. Pain: Physical and Emotional. J Complement Med Alt Healthcare. 9: 555767.
4. Andrew Hague. A new branch of medicine.
5. Andrew Hague. 2017. The Body's Operating System. ARC Journal of Research in Sports Medicine. 2: 16-19. Ref.: <https://bit.ly/2Z7OXsH>
6. Andrew Hague. 2018. Spinal cord injury patient treated with cell-based therapy and CellSonic VIPP. Gen Med Open. Ref.: <https://bit.ly/2EDKUe9>
7. Andrew Hague. Doctors should be paid more.